

Transnational Access project AEGEAN_GAME2

1. General information

Project acronym AEGEAN_GAME2

Project title AEGEAN Pollution: Gaseous and Aerosol airborne MEasurements

Type Scientific project

Scientific theme Physical and chemical processes of polluted air masses over the Aegean Sea during summer period

Main scientific field and Specific discipline Earth Sciences & Environment / Other - Environment

Participants undertaking research

Name + link to id card	Research status	Email	Institution	Institution country	CV	Letter of reference	Publication
		Publication (2)					
		Publication (1)					
	Publication (3)						
COE Hugh	Experienced researcher	hugh.coe@manchester.ac.uk	The University of Manchester	United Kingdom			Publication (1)
KALOGIROS John	Experienced researcher	jkalog@meteo.noa.gr	NOA	Greece			
	Publication (2)						

Lead scientist's background

(scientific and aircraft measurements background and experience, English level) BSc. in Physics, University of Athens, PhD in Environmental Sciences, University of Lancaster. Research interests: Atmospheric Boundary Layer, mean and turbulent characteristics; Urban meteorology; Atmospheric and chemistry transport models. She has been participated in several projects and experimental campaigns where a large number of data segments, have been analysed (e.g. Measurements of wind speed and turbulence to improve wind field and gust spectra prediction models in complex terrain, 1991 – 1993, JOULE I; Sodar development for anemological qualification of complex topography sites suited to installation of medium - large size WTGs, 1994 – 1995, JOULE II).

Recent relevant publications by application group in last 5 years (up to 5)

- [Biskos et al 2009](#)
- [BOSSIOLI ET AL 2009](#)
- [Bougiatioti et al 2009](#)
- [Buzorius et al 2006](#)
- [Morgan et al 2009](#)
- [Tombrou et al 2009](#)

Scientific problems being addressed by the experiments to be performed. Brief summary of the experiments Transport and transformation processes in the Eastern Mediterranean have been the topic of intensive studies that aim to evaluate their impact on regional air quality and visibility, climate and atmospheric composition change (e.g. Mihalopoulos, 2007; Hildebrandt et al., 2010; Pikridas et al., 2010). Though the proper incorporation of these processes in modelling systems is considered critical, it is not always so efficient (Tombrou et al., 2009). We propose to investigate the physical and chemical processing of polluted air transported over the Aegean troposphere during the Etesian winds, and to evaluate the representation of these processes in models of atmospheric composition and transport. The experiment will involve flights of long legs; near surface and close to PBL top, along the direction from Lesvos to Crete (figure) to sample the spatial structure of the atmospheric parameters and of the chemical concentrations. Deep profiles exceeding the PBL top and including 30 minute closed legs at two different levels will provide information regarding radiation balance and flow divergences and fluxes. The interpretation of the airborne measurements will be enriched by the analysis of in situ continuous air pollution and meteorological measurements on the islands of Lesvos and Crete. Furthermore, measurements using instruments onboard commercial vessels commuting across the Aegean Sea will be used. The measured physical parameters and chemical/aerosol concentrations will be compared with model predictions to assess their ability to capture various processes in the atmosphere over the Aegean Sea. This database will provide an excellent tool for further development of parameterization schemes.

Aircraft BAe146 - FAAM

Why this aircraft best suits the experiments? Proposed alternative aircraft The FAAM - BAe146 aircraft is fully equipped with most of the relevant instrumentation needed in order to fulfil our scientific objectives. The aircraft can fly Lagrangian trajectories in the PBL, while continuously monitoring the meteorological conditions and the required physicochemical parameters. The FAAM - BAe146 can fly at relatively low speed, which ensures a high spatial resolution of the observations. A key reason for choosing the FAAM BAE-146 is its large payload that allows complimentary radiation and in situ gaseous and particulate pollution. In particular, we are interested in acquiring measurement of the divergence and fluxes as well as of the concentrations of gaseous pollutants (NO_x, VOC, O₃, SO₂), and the size, concentration and chemical composition (BC, nitrates, sulfates, ammonium, SOA, sea salt, dust) of the aerosol particles over the area. This information will then be used to evaluate input and output model data. Furthermore, the Aerosol Mass Spectrometer during the experiments will provide useful highly time resolved information on the ageing of the aerosol particle in the atmosphere over the Aegean Sea and can deliver information in real time. This would be particularly important due to the high spatial variation of emission sources.

2. Description of the experiments

Scientific objectives / Proposed work / Anticipated output During the prevailing strong north-easterly winds (the so called 'Etesians', the most common synoptic situation that occurs over the Aegean Sea during summer), increased concentrations of gaseous pollutants and aerosol particles are observed, due to the simultaneous contribution of local and distant sources (Salisbury et al., 2003; Kalabokas et al., 2008). This complex mixture of fresh and aged pollution over the Aegean Sea, is mainly controlled by the wind field that is modified by the numerous islands of the Aegean Sea (channel and obstacle effects) and especially Crete (which is oriented perpendicular to the flow) during the Etesians (Kotroni et al., 2001). See also figure below. Previous experiments in the Aegean Sea, which also involve aircraft measurements, were in the framework of STAAARTE-MED and MINOS campaigns. The former covered a north-south path away from the Attica peninsula and easterly of Cyclades, without performing east-west transects (Formenti et al., 2002a; b). The measurement period took place over a decade ago (1998). Meteorological airborne data were not published, while the scientific concern for aerosol focuses on the relationship between SO₂ and sulfates and on direct radiative forcing. Publications related to the MINOS campaign (MINOS special issue) show that flights provided in situ trace gas measurements, while aerosol is not involved in the research linked to this campaign (Ladstätter-Weissenmayer et al., 2003). Previous intensive studies focused mainly on the investigation of long range transport phenomena in the area (Formenti et al., 2002a; Lelieveld et al., 2002; Kocak et al., 2004; Kallos et al., 2007), whereas modelling experiments focusing on the linkage between concentration and atmospheric parameters have been performed mainly with global models (e.g. Roelofs et al., 2003; Lawrence et al., 2003; Scheeren et al., 2003). Recent results of coupling a regional to a global air pollution model have shown that the existing dynamic and chemical processes in modelling systems could not always efficiently represent the observed physical and chemical atmospheric conditions in this area (Tombrou et al., 2009). One of the main difficulties to diagnose the reasons for these discrepancies comes from the fact that only ground measurements are available, thereby limiting the mapping of the dynamic evolution of the PBL. These processes, therefore, warrant the availability of field measurements for the calibration of the models. Our objectives, which differentiate the proposed work from the aforementioned, are to:

- Determine the meteorological atmospheric parameters including turbulence and consequently enhance the knowledge of the PBL evolution over the Aegean Sea, during an Etesian event.
- Measure the current concentrations of gaseous pollutants as well as the physical and chemical properties of the suspended aerosol particles in the area.
- Determine the photochemical oxidants and bulk aerosol entering the boundaries over the Aegean Sea, for regional modelling.
- Determine ozone and SOA increases between the northern and the southern Aegean in order to investigate this ageing.
- Evaluate the dynamic and chemical processes of atmospheric models towards efficient configuration of the physical and chemical profiles (and not just ground data) into the atmosphere of an area where local emissions, medium and long-range transport, as well as stratospheric intrusions shape the atmospheric regime.

The currently proposed work aims at covering the greater Aegean area, through dedicated flights of the FAAM - BAe146 aircraft. Sea traffic emissions mainly around Cyclades and the Attica plume are critical to be involved in the study, as anthropogenic pollution mixes with sea-salt aerosol. The latter is already predicted to offer an important relationship between NO₂ and nitrates, which is also into the research field of this study, unlike previous campaigns. The interpretation of the project results will be enriched by the analysis of ground measurements that will be conducted by the Water and Air Analysis Laboratory (Un. of the Aegean) on the island of Lesvos, sited at the northern Aegean, by the Environmental Chemical Processes Laboratory (Finokalia monitoring station, Un. of Crete) on the island of Crete at the southern Aegean, and onboard commercial vessels.

The monitoring station on Lesvos will provide continuous measurements of gaseous species (i.e., concentrations of O₃, NO_x, and SO₂), aerosol particle properties (i.e., size distributions, volatility, hygroscopicity, and optical properties) as well as meteorological parameters (temperature, relative humidity, wind speed and direction). The monitoring station at Crete will provide ground level measurements of gaseous pollutants (O₃, NO_x, and CO), various aerosol particle parameters (PM₁₀ mass, mass and number size distributions, optical properties, chemical composition measurements), as well as meteorological parameters (temperature, relative humidity, wind speed and direction). The AEGEAN_GAME data will add to the poor experimental data pool for the greater area of Greece. Furthermore, it will comprise a comprehensive description of the three-dimensional structure of both the PBL and pollutants concentrations over the Aegean Sea during Etesian synoptic conditions. Therefore, these data will be valuable to:

- Improve knowledge on the current atmospheric composition and on chemical and dynamic processes occurring in the PBL over the Aegean, during the Etesian regime.

- Validate the atmospheric (WRF) and chemistry transport models (CAMx or WRF-CHEM) under the Etesian synoptic conditions.
- Identify areas of parameterization, which are poorly treated in relation to requirements for air pollution and dispersion applications.
- Improve and validate several parameterization schemes of physical and chemical processes in models (e.g. the radiative transfer code, mixing processes, photolysis rates). In particular, data will be used to explain how efficient do the entrainment mechanism bring air from the dry quasi laminar free atmosphere, into the moist turbulent boundary layer and the role of the existing barriers (islands) to the flow.
- Identify the main requirements for the initial and boundary conditions.

The testing of the models dynamics description will be further supported by diagnostic evaluation (Russell and Dennis, 2000). Specifically, regarding gas-phase chemistry, in situ measurements of indicator species will be used either directly to infer aspects of processes in the atmosphere, or to compare against model-predicted values. For aerosols, the proposed instruments will provide information on their chemical composition as well as the interaction between natural (e.g. sea salt) and anthropogenic (e.g. ship emissions) sources. The information will be used to compare with predicted size-resolved aerosol chemical concentrations (e.g. sulfate, nitrate, ammonium, POA, PEC, SOA, sodium, chloride, crustal; ISORROPIA II and SOAP schemes are used for the partitioning of inorganic and secondary organic aerosols, respectively). The model results will be further elucidated by using Ozone Source Apportionment Technology module to identify the origin of pollution. The vertical profiles of the aerosol, total particle number and size distribution, in combination with the radiation measurements will be used to validate several radiative transfer codes, already included in the meteorological and chemical models, particularly the diffuse radiation, which is generally overestimated by models (Noorian et al., 2008).

Refereed publications in pre-reviewed journal and conference presentations are planned for the dissemination of the scientific results. Several researchers could also use the database in the future.

Weather conditions (e.g. clouds, atmospheric stability, wind speed and direction, weather...) Etesians is the most common synoptic condition that occurs over the Aegean Sea, during summer (especially in July and August), with prevailing winds from the north-eastern direction and clear skies.

Time constraints (time of the day, pass(es) of satellites, weekends, season...) Periods during summer, morning and afternoon hours to study the evolution of the PBL structure and the chemical processes

Location(s) and reason for that choice Map of general area: [Project AEGEAN_GAME: Map](#)

The flights will be performed over the Aegean Sea, Greece, between the northern part of Aegean Sea (island of Lesbos) and Crete. Aegean Sea offers a challenging domain to apply the atmospheric and chemistry transport models, as it is an area 1) with remarkably high levels of air pollution (from anthropogenic and natural sources that interact chemically) from the surface to the top of the troposphere and 2) where the Etesians winds, responsible for the pollution transport from distant sources, are more pronounced (Pinaridi et al., 2005).

Number of flights / flight hours and flight patterns The target area of the aircraft measurements will cover the Aegean area (TR corner: 39°04'40", 26°35'27", (Mytilene airport); BL corner: 35°20'11", 25°08'26", (Heraklion airport, Crete). In total, a minimum of 15 flight hours are requested that correspond to three aircraft missions (~5hrs per mission). The aircraft is proposed to take off from the island of Crete and perform the two flights, measuring at two predefined levels along the main wind direction a) a straight leg near the surface towards the island of Mytilene and b) an intermittent leg close to PBL top with successive paths directly above and below the PBL top (every 50 km) back to Crete. Flights will also involve deep profiles exceeding the PBL top, incorporating 30 minute closed legs (about 50 km diameter) at two different levels (below and above PBL top); a) in the north of Crete and b) approximately halfway between Lesbos and Crete. One flight is proposed during the morning hours (~ 0500–1100LT) and the second one during the afternoon hours (~ 1300–1800LT). A supplementary third flight is proposed to cover east-west transects above the greater Cycladic area during daylight (~1100–1600LT).

Other constraints or requirements

3. Key measurements required to achieve science aims

Parameter / measurement required Basic meteorological instrumentation of FAAM - BAe146 (temperature, wind, humidity and turbulence sensors) is needed to interpret the structure of the atmospheric PBL over the Aegean Sea during the Etesian winds. Together with the solar and terrestrial radiative fluxes, the meteorological measurements will be used to test existing PBL parameterization schemes. The analysis of the aerosol particle number concentrations and size distribution at different levels, in combination with the radiation measurements will be used to validate the radiative transfer codes: particularly the diffuse radiation code, which is generally overestimated by models.

Concentration measurements of background pollutants such as O₃ and CO are necessary to validate the physical processes (e.g. transport, mixing, stratified layers) in the atmospheric transport models. Measurements of NO_y speciated species will contribute to the identification of the photochemical efficiency and the origin of the air masses (fresh emissions, aged, transported). The sampling and analysis of NMHC (WAS) is important for tracing the origin of organic species (anthropogenic, natural) but also for estimating the reactivity of the organic mixture at different locations.

Aerosol size distribution (DMT-PCASP), collected at different levels, will serve for the identification of aerosols from various origins. The Black carbon content (using the PSAP instrument) is important in case of a potential biomass burning event as influences the absorption of solar radiation. A single particle soot photometer will be available and will make measurements of black carbon mass and deliver information on its size distribution and mixing state. We will be able to chemically resolve the submicron aerosol mass and deliver its size distribution using the Aerosol Mass Spectrometer (AMS), providing mass loadings of sulphates, nitrates, ammonium and organic mass. Filter samples will be collected for analysis of a range of inorganic ions, including sodium and chloride. These measurements will allow us to capture the chemical interaction between sea salt aerosol (sodium chloride) and anthropogenic pollution (sulfuric and nitric acid produced from SO₂ and NO_x emitted from humans) towards secondary aerosol production (sulfate, and nitrate).

If applicable, specify TA instrument required None

Instruments to be provided by hosting aircraft operator (basic instrumentation owned by the aircraft operator described on EUFAR website only) Information is included in the attached file FAAM-Instruments

Instruments to be provided by scientific group (Have already been flown. On which aircraft? Do the instruments have their own data acquisition system?) An Aerodyne Compact Time of Flight Aerosol Mass Spectrometer (C-AMS) is already part of the FAAM BAE-146 fit and has successfully flown in a number of studies since 2004 (Crosier et al 2007; Capes et al., 2008; Morgan et al., 2010a and Morgan et al., 2010b). The instrument has already been approved on the aircraft and has a standalone data system. The University of Manchester also

maintain and operate a Scanning Mobility Particle Sizer (SMPS) on the same rack as the C-AMS. UOM will also operate this instrument for AEGEAN-GAME.

A DMT Single particle soot photometer uses an intra cavity laser to heat and subsequently incandesce absorbing particles. The light from the incandescence is proportional to the mass of BC in a single particle. Information on the mixing state of black carbon can also be obtained. This instrument has been successfully operated on the BAE-146 aircraft for the last 3 years (McMeeking et al., 2010). The University of Manchester has agreed to provide an operator for these instruments.

Instrument operators onboard (in addition to those provided by the aircraft operator). If so, how many? 3

If applicable, plans for simultaneous field work plans / ground equipment to be used University of the Aegean (UOA): Water and Air Analysis Laboratory

Ground level measurements of gaseous pollutants (O₃, NO_x, and SO₂), various aerosol particle parameters (size distributions and optical properties of fine and ultra fine particles), as well as meteorological parameters (temperature, relative humidity, wind speed and direction) will be performed at the monitoring station of the Water and Air Analysis Laboratory of the Un. of the Aegean on Lesvos simultaneously with the flight measurements. Concentrations of O₃, NO_x, and SO₂ will be monitored with commercial gas analyzers (API, Models M400, M200, and M100, respectively). Size distribution measurements of aerosol particles will be measured with a Scanning Mobility Particles Sizer (TSI, Model 3034) an Optical Particle Counter (Grimm, Model 1.08) and an 11-stage cascade impactor, whereas the scattering coefficient of the aerosol particles at three wavelengths will be determined by a commercial Nephelometer (TSI, Model 3653). Finally, the volatility and the hygroscopicity of the particles will be determined using a custom-made Tandem DMA (HTDMA) system. In addition, measurements of the concentration and the size distribution of the particles having diameter greater than 300 nm will be provided by an Optical Particle Counter (Grimm, Model 1.08) that will be installed onboard a commercial ship vessel running through the Aegean Sea at the same days as the proposed measurements.

University of Crete: Environmental Chemical Processes Laboratory

Ground level measurements of gaseous pollutants (O₃, NO_x, and CO), various aerosol particle parameters (PM₁₀ mass, mass and number size distributions, optical properties, chemical composition measurements), as well as meteorological parameters (temperature, relative humidity, wind speed and direction) will be performed at the monitoring station of University of Crete located at Finokalia, Crete (<http://finokalia.chemistry.uoc.gr/>). Concentrations of O₃, CO and NO_x, will be monitored with commercial gas analyzers (Thermoelectron). Size distribution measurements of aerosol particles will be measured with a Scanning Mobility Particles Sizer and a 11-stages cascade impactor, whereas the scattering and absorption coefficients of the aerosol particles will be determined by commercial Nephelometer (Radiance research) and aethalometer (PSAP). Finally complete chemical composition measurements (ions, trace metals, organic and elemental carbon) will be performed on filters collected on a 6-h basis during the flight days.

4. Data processing and analysis

Methodology for handling the data and analysis of output (*airborne data acquisition, ground-truthing / observations, data processing and interpretation*) Aircraft operators will perform the airborne measurements. For the non-core instruments, the instruments' operators will be responsible.

The quality control, calibration and primary analysis of meteorological measurements will be coordinated by the PI J. Kalogiros and if necessary in the framework of collaboration with NCAR institute (Dr. Julien Sun). Some basic calibration maneuvers (speed run, reverse heading, attack angle and sidlip maneuvers) for the turbulence probe above PBL top at the start or the end of the flight will be needed. Calibration of the SMPS systems that will be employed for the ground measurements will be made calibrating the flows of the system (with a bouble flow meter) and checking with standard monodisperse particles. The HTDMA will be calibrated with laboratory generated pure salt particles (e.g., NaCl or (NH₄)₃SO₄). The data analysis of the ground chemical measurements will be supported by the two PIs N. Mihalopoulos and G. Biskos.

The University of Manchester will be responsible for operating the C-AMS, SMPS and SP-2 on the FAAM BAE-146 aircraft. Manchester staff will collect the data, calibrate the instrument and perform the quality assurance of the data.

Our team can undertake the filter sampling set up as well as the chemical analysis of the aerosol particles collected on the filters.

The final data analysis and comparison with models' parameterizations will be processed by the NKUA and UOA

? Present 3D meteorological parameters fields for PBL

? Present 3D concentration fields

? Provide along flight track concentration fields for direct comparison to 4D atmospheric chemistry transport model simulated concentration fields

? Enable in situ cross calibration with other ground-based and airborne observations

The results from the proposed experiments will be published at meteorology, atmospheric chemistry and aerosol science journals (e.g. Boundary-Layer Meteorology, Atmosph. Env., Atm. Chem. & Phys., J. Aerosol Sci., etc). It is expected that several publications, each investigating different aspects of the gas and aerosol phase chemical formation and atmospheric processes taking place over the Aegean Sea, will be the outcome of this study.

Resources available to support the project beyond the flying/data acquisition period (*funding, cooperation with other projects, manpower for analysis of results and preparation of user report, availability of laboratory facilities...*) NKUA: A researcher (project-funded) and a fraction of three permanent researchers' time (two at postdoctoral stage, one PhD student) will be dedicated for the management of the data, data analysis, preparation of the reports, and scientific papers. Szabó-Takács Beata will also collaborate with NKUA and contribute to all the undertaken tasks. The NKUA team has long experience in model simulations and access to the necessary infrastructure in order to perform the simulations.

UOA: The instruments at the monitoring station of the Un. of the Aegean will be available to support the proposed campaign. A postdoc and a PhD student from the university will be responsible for these measurements. They will also provide the ground-truthing based on the supplementary in situ observations at the Lesvos island.

UoC: The instruments at the monitoring station of the Un. of Crete will be available to support the proposed campaign. A postdoc and a PhD student from the university will be responsible for these measurements.

NOA: A researcher will support the part of the project related to meteorology-turbulence measurements.

Manchester/FGAM: The Manchester component of the National Centre for Atmospheric Sciences (NCAS) has an interest in the transport and transformation of pollution aerosol through an element of the UK's national research programme. UOM agrees to offer expertise in the analysis and interpretation of the data and integration.

NKUA, UOA and UoC will collaborate to develop a dataset available for further scientific studies.

The four PIs will also dispose a fraction of their time to project management, post-campaign analysis and dissemination of results.

Proposals (not clustered with AEGEAN_GAME) for additional funding are being submitted in a national research framework.

5. Planning

Starting date: 29-08-2011

Ending date: 08-09-2011

Preferred and acceptable dates (*season / time windows*) 15/07/2011- 20/08/2011. We are flexible on dates

Agreement to share aircraft time (*project clustering, cost sharing*) Yes

6. Other useful comments

Training benefit of the project (*e.g. spread potential of airborne research to a wide scientific community; training of research students in experimental planning, methodology, data analysis and applications, etc*) Most of the participants do not have experience in airborne data acquisition. Therefore, the proposed work provides excellent training opportunities to the students and new postdoctoral researchers involved. They will gain experience in the planning and execution of a major aircraft experiment and the understanding of aircraft observation techniques. In addition, in post-campaign analysis the project will provide a unique and scientifically exciting database for use in and comparison with state-of-the-art models. Through this experiment, all the members involved will gain expertise in handling large databases, running complex numerical models. Through conference and journal publication the students and postdocs will gain skills in written and oral presentations. In addition, two group members from UOA and NKUA wish to participate in the flights preparation and if possible in the flights. At least three researchers (PhD students and PostDoc) will participate in EUFAR schools for data analysis, training actively work on the data analysis and interpretation of the results.

If possible, 3 scientific reviewers that EUFAR may contact Professor Scot Martin

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Sources of funding of the project and of related projects (*if clustering with existing projects supported either by national or other EC funding, how the project add additional or complementary aims to the already funded experiments*) The amount of money needed to cover the AVAPS Dropsondes' expenses (2.500 euro) is already allocated by NKUA. Furthermore, most members of the research team have a permanent position at the University, thus they will support this project merely for scientific reasons. Finally, in case this proposal is accepted, its outcome could be used as input to forthcoming national calls and funds.

Scientific training provided by lead scientist to other EUFAR sponsored scientists within the fields of the proposed experiments and analysis Yes

Number of students 3

Number of days recommended 4

Knowledge about EUFAR opportunities from From your colleagues

Related documents

You may need to login to the EUFAR Back Office to see all the documents.

- [Project AEGEAN_GAME2: FAAM Instruments](#)
- [Project AEGEAN_GAME2: References](#)

7. Reporting

Campaign dates: From 29-08-2011 to 08-09-2011

Participants

Name	First time flying this aircraft	Participation in the campaign	Number of visits to campaign	Duration of stay	T&S reimbursed	Additional information
TOMBROU-TZELL A Maria	Yes	On site	2	14	Yes	
ATHANASOPOULOU Eleni	Yes	Remotely	0	0	No	Not participating at this stage
BISKOS George	Yes	Remotely	0	0	No	In charge of the ground station at Limnos
BOSSIOLI Elizabeth	No	On site	1	10	Yes	
COE Hugh	No	On site	1	14	Yes	J. Allan and A. Bacak were on site (substitutes for Hugh Coe)
DANDOU Aggeliki	Yes	Remotely	0	0	No	
KALOGIROS John	Yes	On site	1	5	Yes	
MIHALOPOULOS Nikolaos	Yes	Remotely	0	0	No	In charge of the ground station at Finokalia
PROTONOTARIOU Anna	No	Remotely	0	0	No	
SZABO-TAKACS Beata	Yes	Remotely	0	0	No	

Meetings

Start date	End date	Location	Title	Number of persons from the group attending the meeting	Overall number of attendees
25-07-2011	26-07-2011	Chania, Crete	preliminary visit	1	3
27-08-2011	09-09-2011	Chania, Crete	campaign	3	20

Confirmation of the user access (list of flights, number of flight hours) / Evaluation of the service provided by the operator: mark (1-Unsatisfactory, 2-Insufficient, 3-Satisfactory, 4-Good, 5-Excellent) and comments

Three flights of a similar route covered the eastern and western parts of the Aegean Sea. Two flights were performed on the same day to study the impact of the diurnal cycle. The total number of flight hours were 13hours and 20min for the AEGEAN-GAME. We have also processed the data collected during the other 3 projects. The crew and the scientists in charge were outstanding and put an enormous effort to overcome some of the difficulties encountered. Evaluation: 4.5

Quality of data and associated service

Data preprocessing detected frequent spikes in the INS/GPS data which then propagated to the wind turbulence data. Similar problems were also observed in dew point hygrometer and sea surface temperature. There were also time gaps in the CR2 Buck hygrometer. The Lyman-alpha hygrometer was saturated at the near sea legs probably due to humidity on its window. The nephelometer had probably pressure problems during the first flight and it was not measuring above a certain altitude. A good dataset was obtained with the AMS and associated SMPS, with the only outage on flight B640, caused by a software fault affecting the valves on the inlet system.

Main achievements / Further plans for analysis

Data preprocessing included detection of spikes and time gaps in data and filling by interpolation, synchronization of INS/GPS data with radome wind probe data, using pressure-altitude and airspeed-ground speed correlation, calibration of fast humidity sensor Lyman-alpha using a second order polynomial with a drifting average voltage by comparison with the corresponding slow sensor (GE mirror hygrometer) and correction of SST for water vapor path effects due to flight altitude above sea surface using sounding data. The radome probe was calibrated using the flight maneuvers. The calibration of the differential pressure sensors showed significant offsets (which varied a little between flights according to data while the aircraft was steady on the ground) and slope quite different than unity for the sideslip pressure differential. Absolute (static and dynamic) pressure sensors were corrected for static pressure defect which had a significant offset. This had a significant effect on the accuracy of horizontal wind components as it was verified by the reverse heading maneuver. The attack flow angle was calibrated for the upwash effect by the aircraft wing. This calibration was eddy-frequency dependant in order to include the variable aerodynamic effects with eddy- frequency. Offsets in INS/GPS attitude data were checked using data while the aircraft was on ground and running in the runway and were found to be small. Wind data were recalculated with the new radome calibration. The new estimated horizontal wind components differ up to 3 m s⁻¹ from the wind provided by FAAM routines and calibration depending on the wind direction relative to aircraft heading. The vertical wind velocity estimated by FAAM had a 0.5 m s⁻¹ bias which was not seen in the new estimated vertical wind velocity. In addition, small power spectrum differences, especially at high eddy frequencies, were found between the two calculations of wind components. The validity of new wind calculations against FAAM calculations was also verified by observing the estimated wind components before and after aircraft turns when FAAM calculations showed differences in the estimated wind components but not in the

new calculations. Significant mass concentrations were recorded in the boundary layer, with particles mainly composed of ammonium sulphate and organic matter. The preliminary data has been processed and made available to the project participants. Analysis is currently going on. Conferences Tombrou M., Bossioli E., Kalogiros J., Allan J., Bacak A., Biskos G., Coe H., Dandou A., Kouvarakis G., Mihalopoulos N., Protonotariou A.P., Szabó-Takács B., Triantafyllou E., 2012, Physical and chemical processes of polluted air masses during Etesians: Aegean-Game airborne campaign - An outline, COMECAP 2012, Athens, Greece Protonotariou A. P., Tombrou M., Bossioli E., Mihalopoulos N., Biskos G., Kalogiros J., Kouvarakis G. & Amiridis V., 2012, Air pollution in Eastern Mediterranean: nested-grid GEOS-CHEM model results and airborne observations, COMECAP 2012, Athens, Greece

Difficulties encountered

We faced flight restrictions by the Greek Civil Aviation Administration, especially during the first flight. In fact, we could not fly lower than 300m during the first flight, while, during the other two flights we could not go lower than 150m. In addition, the use of dropsondes was restricted to altitudes above 300m.